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D5.10

WP5 - Translation of results into policy

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1 Short abstract

Examples of results of the aligned studies are visualised in the HBM4EU indicator reports. Indicators - based on the distributions of exposure data, their comparison with available health-based guidance values and comparisons between regions and over time - allow for the monitoring of internal exposure and impact of chemicals as measured in several Human Biomonitoring studies in different EU-regions. These indicators are important new outputs of the HBM4EU project.

In this deliverable, we report the reflections of policy makers and stakeholders and - in an early stage - on the relevance and usefulness of the indicators from their perspective.

The process of developing this deliverable consisted of three stages. The key stage was that we sent out questionnaires to experts, policy makers and societal stakeholders. We asked them questions like: Which conclusions should be drawn from the indicators? What is seen as most relevant? Which information could be highlighted by the researchers in order to facilitate the uptake of results and implementation in policy terms or in managerial and professional practices? In short, we asked them to appraise the results on their relevance for policy and for society.

In order to guide and structure the appraisal exercise, relevant criteria were defined in a preliminary stage, stage 1. To check the robustness of these criteria, a consultation was organised within the HBM4EU consortium to evaluate the criteria in terms of relevance, clarity and completeness. These criteria were mentioned in questionnaires that were sent to a diversity of experts, policy actors and societal stakeholders in key stage 2.

In an additional stage 3, we asked participants of the online HBM4EU workshop on 30-31 March 2022 to fill out a shortened online questionnaire, also aiming to appraise the presented results of the HBM4EU aligned study on their relevance for policy and society. This workshop was organised by VITO, EEA and UAntwerpen and discussed the Aligned Study results for Cadmium, Bisphenols, Phthalates and DINCH, and PFAS.

Results of this 'appraisal process' (in stages 1, 2 and 3) are summarised in this deliverable.

When comparing the signal value of the Aligned Study results on the substance groups discussed, we see that the results on **PFAS** triggers comparatively more societal concern than the other substances groups. This need for policy action is highly underlined during the workshop and in the online survey that was taken from the participants (stage 3). The discussion on **Phthalates/DINCH** is in another stage of policy-making. Phthalates have been regulated for a longer time, but from the monitoring results it becomes clear that phthalates can still be found in every single sample investigated. It looks like the policy actions that have been taken, are not effective enough. Based on the workshop discussions and the survey results, we draw the conclusion that **Bisphenols**, even after 30 years of attention and the implementation of extensive regulations, still provokes societal controversy. Respondents underline the need for more investment in solid risk assessment, as there still is uncertainty and controversy on the hazard thresholds. From all the substance groups discussed, **Cadmium** is the substance group of which respondents state that the Aligned Study only have "moderate" signal value. Cadmium is one of the 'old' chemicals: it had been regulated already a long time, but from monitoring results it appears that the levels have not dropped significantly over the last 10 years, which incites concern on potential health effects for several population groups.

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2 Introduction

After 2 previous cases that were organised by means of intense two-day workshops (see [Deliverable D5.4](#) reporting on the workshop on bisphenols and phthalates in 2019 and [Deliverable D5.7](#) reporting on the online workshop on PFAS in 2021), this 3rd case of phased action planning showcases a written mode for facilitating the further interpretation and policy translation of HBM4EU results. The overall goal of this written case study is to appraise the policy and societal relevance of aligned studies results as priorities for further action. Examples of results of the aligned studies are visualised in the indicator reports. These indicators are important new outputs of the HBM4EU project, and with this exercise we seize the opportunity to highlight these results among policy makers and stakeholders and give them a say in their relevance and usefulness of HBM results in an early stage.

The first section of this deliverable D5.10 deals with the overall process architecture and the criteria that may be used for appraising and prioritising aligned studies results as visualised in indicator reports (chapter 1). The second section describes the first consultation on the relevant criteria and the summary of the input we received from T5.4 and T5.5 colleagues (chapter 2). The third section describes the content of the second consultation aimed at respondents from distinct bodies of HBM4EU that represent the science-policy nexus: the management team, the policy board and the stakeholder forum (chapter 3). The fourth section describes the third consultation of participants of the 30-31 March 2022 online workshop organised by VITO, EEA, and UAntwerpen (chapter 4).

The reasons why we intend to have these consultations are at least twofold. (1) Because we expect that the HBM4EU indicators will be interpreted and used in different ways after their release and we value the stakeholders' appraisal as an interesting source of additional information. (2) Results of the HBM4EU aligned studies will anyway be contextualised in the diversity of European

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and national policy, in relation to other types of knowledge, previous policy initiatives, knowledge about solutions and societal concerns. Moreover, different opinions and considerations may exist, especially where policy options are still under negotiation or where uncertainty issues play a role. We would like to prospect and create transparency on this scientific, policy and societal significance and to stimulate the extraction of conclusions or main messages.

The ultimate goal of the consultations is not to rank or prioritise substance groups, nor to use a fixed multi-criteria assessment methodology, but to map the divergence of opinions on the results obtained from the different chemicals, based on people's reading of the HBM indicator reports.

Which conclusions should be drawn from the indicators? What will be seen as most relevant? Which information could be highlighted by the researchers in order to facilitate the uptake and implementation in policy terms or in managerial and professional practices? Researchers are used to indicate the statistical significance and the comparison of exposure to chemicals with guidance values as a baseline for interpretation. But how will the graphs be received and perceived by professional experts, policy makers and the public at large? A big diversity of factors can be drivers or preconditions of policy response. Once identified, these factors could also be used as criteria to prioritise HBM4EU results or to strengthen the sense of urgency for the uptake of research results by policy makers.

By launching these consultations, we aim to: increase insight into the level of agreement on the solidity of the knowledge base, identify specific policy opportunities and give clarity on the societal desire to take policy action given the new Human Biomonitoring results from the aligned studies. This exercise can also increase awareness on the results among a broader diversity of actors. Such an appraisal is therefore clearly different from and complementary to the 3 fruitful processes on research priorities (on substances) of HBM4EU in which responsible governments and national hubs participated.

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3 Stage 1: Consultation on the criteria (list) for the appraisal of policy relevance

3.1 Aim and process

UAntwerpen drafted a set of potential criteria on the base of previous exercises in Flanders in the context of the FLEHS campaigns (Keune et al, 2009; Coertjens et al, 2018) and insights from state-of-the-art literature in the domain of risk governance (such as Klinke & Renn 2002; Renn 2005; Renn 2017; De Hollander & Hanemaaijer 2003, Sumner et al., Health Research Policy and Systems 2011). The use of criteria enables a systematic and transparent deliberation on the many relevant HBM-results for further interpretation and action planning.

In order to do so, we invited researchers from T5.5 and T5.4 partners for feedback on the draft list of scientific, societal and policy criteria for policy uptake. The scope in this stage was generic, regardless of specific chemical substance indicator reports. The output strived for was a solid list of criteria.

3.2 The questionnaire on the criteria list (1st stage)

The list for consultation was organised in a written questionnaire format. In concrete terms, we wanted to hear from the respondents whether the list of criteria was sufficiently solid and/or still needed adjustment before asking different types of stakeholders to fill it out. We listed up 3 categories of criteria and exemplified sub-criteria and explanation for clarification. The respondents could indicate by a yes or a no whether the criterion seemed relevant to them and whether they had specific comments or examples in mind with regard to that criterion. We also added open fields, to verify whether the respondent missed criteria in the different categories, whether differentiation would be desirable for application at the EU-level versus the member state level (as for instance was mentioned by a respondent for health concern expressed as 'risk' or for issues in hot spot areas). We also left room for adding additional questions or comments.

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We explicitly opted for a Word version and not for an online survey format (e.g. Qualtrics survey or Google Forms) because we wanted the respondents to comment in and between the fields of the different sections. The consultation was also data-protected. For the recipients being research partners in WP5, an ethical clearance nor an informed consent were necessary. We also only used their input on an aggregated level and did not link the answers to person names or affiliations in research output or deliverables.

Nr.	Criterion: <u>Note:</u> in the end these criteria will serve as questions to ask for feedback from experts in a specific substance group	Relevant aspects/sub-criteria may include:
1	Scientific relevance	
1.1	Health concern (hazard)	Type of effects, exceedance of HBGV's, time trends, vulnerability of specific groups, ...
1.2	Extent of the risk	Population(s) at risk, susceptibility, number(s) of exposed people, persistency, impact on future generations, ...
1.3	Scientific evidence and robustness	Robust knowledge on exposure-effect associations, knowledge on sources and exposure pathways, acquired consensus under scientific peers ...
1.4	Complexity and scientific uncertainty	Knowledge- and data gaps, scientific uncertainty, disagreement between expert groups
2	Societal relevance	
2.1	Risk perception	Public concern, willingness to act
2.2	Societal resonance	Agenda-setting at political level, by civil society organisations and networks and/or in the media, social amplification of risk
2.3	Social inequality in exposure, effects, risk	Higher health risk or concerns for socially vulnerable groups?
2.4	Socio-economic consequences	Socio-economic and vested interests;
2.5	Costs of inaction expected	Impactful (monetary health) costs of inaction expected for sectors
2.6	Normative character	Diversity of opinions on the issue based on differences in norms and values
2.7	Emerging practices	Professional practices (popping up or vested) already taking this knowledge into account
3	Policy relevance	
3.1	Collective (preventive) action or health promotion is possible	Opportunities for intervention via environmental or chemical policy or health prevention promotion
3.2	Consensus on appropriate responses	Agreement on policy options, measures, interventions

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Nr.	Criterion: <u>Note:</u> in the end these criteria will serve as questions to ask for feedback from experts in a specific substance group	Relevant aspects/sub-criteria may include:
3.3	Existing policy already (partly) in place	Current policy processes and agreed policy initiatives at different policy levels (European – local)
3.4	Need for (additional or novel) policy	Maturity of current policy: underdeveloped, in full development, well-developed
3.5	Multi-level character	Policy levels authorised to act, the policy level differentiation. Not only relevant for EU-actors but also national/regional initiatives needed
3.6	Need for more cooperation and policy integration	Transversal nature of the policy theme, policy areas or policy sectors involved
3.7	Need for more multi-actor cooperation	Interdependency of public and private actors to develop and implement policy initiative
3.8	Costs of inaction expected	Impactful budgetary costs of inaction expected for the public sector
3.9	Political salience	Interest and sensitivity of the issue for <i>political</i> decision makers beyond agencies and the administration (for instance in parliament, for political families)

We received feedback of 5 participants out of 16 recipients from 4 different institutes. Their responses were used to produce an updated version.

- A number of technical remarks have been addressed, especially with regard to distinct types of health effects and risk concepts for the category health concerns and extent of the risk. The original distinction between health concern (hazard) and extent of the risk was transformed in 3 categories for a better assimilation to the indicator report's information; exposure concern, health concern (hazard) and extent of the risk.
- The demand for more clarification on some of the criteria was granted; the definitions were adapted for the second (stage 2) version. Also, the purpose of criteria like 'normative character', 'emerging practices', 'political salience' was not clear enough as well how this criterion would eventually be assessed. There however is a distinction to be made between delivering a personal opinion/estimation on the relevance of the criterion and providing desk research information that would assess the criterion. This would lead to a much more intense and longer process for the indicator's appraisal. It could be helpful indeed as a respondent notified, to keep for instance the public, political or societal consensus in mind when you have to decide which sort of criterion to focus on but not having all the information available yet on the sets of criteria makes the criteria rather hypothetical. That however is what social scientists would appraise as *ex ante* relevant for policy uptake.
- The generic character of the criteria list was not obvious for everyone, making the application or delineation of the assignment unclear: should the questions be answered strictly for the indicators as presented or more broadly/general with regard to the knowledge on a chemical substance and the contribution of this indicator reports to the quality of this knowledge base? The fact that HBM4EU does not deal with every feature or issue of chemicals (for instance

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persistence) does not imply that respondents cannot reflect on the significance of these indicators for the broader characteristics of chemical substances.

- Some respondents argued for a merger of some of the criteria, for instance on 'the costs of inaction' expected or with regard to the 'risk perception' criteria, or the types of policy innovation necessary (across policy domains, across policy levels). Others on the other hand advocated additional differentiation on the criterion, for instance for appraising the scientific evidence for exposure-effects (more linked to hazard) separately from scientific evidence about exposure pathway and sources. In these cases, we opted for the most unambiguous formulation in order to avoid misinterpretations.
- Unfortunately, we could not make a statistic with 5 participants. Moreover, not all respondents completed the columns, although they provided very relevant input.

All the input was carefully processed for the questionnaire of the second stage.

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4 Stage 2: consultation on HBM results as visualised by HBM4EU-indicator reports

4.1 Aim and process

The second stage of the process is set up as a multi-criteria mapping. A mapping is to be distinguished from an assessment. The reflection on the quality of knowledge base and the societal and policy relevance does not allow a too standardised approach. The objective and as a consequence the output should inform regulators, policy makers and stakeholders on the different context for each of the substance groups. We avoided giving the impression that the one substance group is more important than the other. Moreover, this consultation was decided to be organised for the 3 or 4 chemical substance groups with a health-based HBM Guidance Value (HBM-GV) available. This focus on part of the total group of chemical substances does not legitimise a ranking, because other substance groups (without an HBM Guidance Value available) might also be of very high health concern for policy making. We can think of differences in geographic distributions or between age groups in exposure to hazardous chemicals, even if we do not have yet obtained solid exposure responses from human studies or from animal toxicity data.

A transparent and ex ante mapping of policy relevance of substance group results as visualised by the indicators rather highlights the (expected) specific policy context for every substance group and allows for a comparative perspective on the HBM4EU results.

For this multi-criteria mapping the questionnaire was sent to scientific experts to appraise the visualised HBM indicators for the scientific criteria, policy actors for the policy-relevant criteria and societal stakeholders for the societal criteria. Given the preliminary and still confidential character of the aligned study results and indicator reports we opted for the consultation of the members of the management board, the EU policy board and the stakeholder forum in the HBM4EU-configuration. Respondents were asked to treat all information confidentially in this stage.

In Autumn 2021, the invitation and questionnaire were sent out to the HBM4EU management board, the policy board and the stakeholder forum, together with the indicator reports on 3 substance groups (PFAS, Cadmium, and Phthalates/DINCH). As we clearly experienced during the previous workshops that researchers and experts can witness from different roles, we also allowed and even encouraged cross-section filling out the questionnaires. Indeed, complementary to this usual division of tasks, we acknowledge that environmental health researchers operate as boundary workers towards policy needs. These experts are often well informed on societal concerns and political agenda opportunities, based on their day-to-day experience working on the interface of science and policy. Further we acknowledge that policy makers used to work with Human Biomonitoring and public advocacy groups may also have a good overview of relevant environmental health knowledge; they also know how to formulate and raise policy relevant research-oriented questions. This explains why we planned to create openness for 'cross-border' filling out the criteria-list in a next stage. Respondents got the opportunity to provide input on all 3 categories: scientific relevance, societal relevance and policy relevance.

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Although there was this openness on cross-border filling out, we detected challenges with regard to the policy translation of messages as formulated in the indicator fiches. Voiced from a stakeholder perspective, a stronger interplay was expected between the research result's presentation and the policy needs. Some recommendations were expressed with regard to the indicator fiches as such. This indicator information was very much welcomed, but an even stronger focus was suggested on the public and policy makers as the main target groups of this information. The following suggestions might serve as a source of inspiration: to remove non-essential methodological information and abbreviations, to provide a more complete summary of the study results and topical messages using headlines, including items on the main uses and main exposure sources of the substance group and the policy issues as described in the questionnaire. This kind of information is in principle available in the scoping documents, but in response to the recommendations made, the organisers of the 30-31 March HBM4EU workshop actively took them into account in developing the workshop's presentations. These research outcomes (available separately at the HBM4EU website) could also be merged for this objective. Next to that, we also recommend to keep both types of information closely together: the more accessible summaries and headlines on the one hand and the more methodological background information (as an Appendix or hyperlink) on the other. The reason behind this combination is that the broader audience will also get informed by social and environmental movement organisations that do read expert information.

4.2 The questionnaire for the appraisal of indicator results (2nd stage)

In the first stage, we consulted the respondents regardless of specific chemical substance groups. During the second stage, the specific context for each substance group is essential and for that reason we transformed the criteria list in a more extended questionnaire format.

We acknowledged that in some cases the criterion can be interpreted positively (adding to the argument that policy uptake of the indicator results is needed) or negatively (giving arguments

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contra), regardless of its binary character or the use of grades. Consider for instance the criterion of remaining scientific uncertainty or disagreement: this can be a disadvantage for policy uptake but also a good reason to apply the precautionary principle. Therefore, it was important to offer the respondents clearness on the direction of the criteria.

Also, for this second stage, we explicitly opted for a Word version and not an online survey format because we wanted the respondents to comment in and between the fields of the different sections. This enabled the respondent to provide a comment, an example or a good reference for documenting the particular criterion in the context of the specific chemical substance group. And again, we left room for adding a) additional criteria for appraising the health concern and its policy context, b) whether a differentiation is considered necessary for appraising the 'risk' geographically, for a 'hot spot' approach, or for the potential and scope for additional measures under national/regional/local governance and c) missing information or clearness. Last but not least, we started the questionnaire with an invite to edit a tweet on the indicator results for the chemical substance: a core message for colleagues of the respondent's own organisation and a separate one for the public at large.

The consultation is data-protected. We only used the input on an aggregated level and did not link the answers to person names or affiliations. The ethics guidelines in the HBM4EU project include general recommendations for research activities in a Social Sciences and Humanities-context (see Appendix 1).

Consultations of HBM4EU-bodies are object of the rules that count in the governance structure. A paragraph on ethical aspects is recommended, but no ethical clearance required for this type of consultations as the positions, roles and functionalities of for instance the Stakeholder forum are described in the project's internal rules.

We only added a few questions and fields for the identification of the respondent's background: whether they identified themselves as environment/health experts or risk assessor, as societal stakeholder, or as a regulatory and/or policy expert or risk manager. This identification guides the respondents through the 3 parts (categories of criteria) of the questionnaire. In case of more than one affiliation respondents could rank them and opt for filling out more parts.

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Nr.	Criterion	Question + definitions or relevant sub-criteria
1	Scientific relevance	
1.1	Exposure concern Think of: number(s) of people exposed, geographical distribution, time trends, higher exposed subgroups of population, knowledge on sources, lifestyle and exposure pathways ...	To what extent do the values of the HBM4EU indicator on [name chemical substance] legitimise an increased <u>exposure concern</u>?
1.2	Health concern (hazard) Also think of type of effects, mixture effects, persistence of substance, type of vulnerable groups, ...	To what extent do the values of the HBM4EU indicator on [name chemical substance] legitimise an increased <u>health concern</u>?
1.3	Extent of the risk Risk = hazard * exposure. Think of numbers or % exposed exceeding HBM-GV, but if no exceedance also the relevance for health impacts, groups or behaviour patterns correlated with higher risk, population(s) at risk, burden of disease, impact on future generations, ...	To what extent do the values of the HBM4EU indicator on [name chemical substance] legitimise an increased <u>risk concern</u>?
1.4	Scientific evidence and robustness of knowledge base with regard to hazard (exposure-effect associations) Evidence refers to sufficient, robust expert knowledge and also to acquired consensus under scientific peers, ...	Do the values of the HBM4EU indicator on [name chemical substance] in your opinion strengthen the evidence base or knowledge robustness with regard to hazard (exposure-effect associations) for risk management or policy measures?
1.5	Scientific evidence and robustness of knowledge base with regard to exposure pathways and sources Evidence refers to sufficient, robust expert knowledge and also to acquired consensus under scientific peers, ...	Do the values of the HBM4EU indicator on [name chemical substance] in your opinion strengthen the evidence base or knowledge robustness with regard to exposure pathways and sources for risk management or policy measures?
1.6	Knowledge gaps and scientific uncertainty Notwithstanding the available scientific evidence, there can still be relevant knowledge- and data gaps, scientific uncertainty, or remaining disagreement between expert groups on one or more of the items 1.1-1.3, as observable in scientific literature, studies, on conferences, ...	Do you still see knowledge gaps or scientific uncertainty in the knowledge base on [name substance group] that might hamper additional risk management or policy measures? (despite the information presented in the HBM4EU indicator)?
2	Societal relevance	
2.1	Risk perception As a driver for risk management and policy making, willingness to act, possibility to act (labelling, SIN-list, ...)?	How relevant in your opinion with regard to [name chemical substance] is public concern of consumers or citizens

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Nr.	Criterion	Question + definitions or relevant sub-criteria
2.2	Societal resonance Think of civil society organisations/networks pressing on the public/political agenda, NGO activity, attention for [name chemical substance] in the media, social amplification of risk	How relevant in your opinion is lobbying by civil society organisations as a driver for risk management and policy making on [name chemical substance]?
2.3	Social inequality in exposure, effects, risk	Do you consider higher health risk or concerns for <i>socially</i> vulnerable groups (lower SES) a good driver for risk management measures or policy making with regard to [name chemical substance]?
2.4	Socio-economic consequences	How much relevance or impact in your opinion have socio-economic and vested interests on dealing with additional risk regulation, management and policy with regard to [name chemical substance] ?
2.5	Costs of inaction expected	Do you expect impactful (monetary health) costs of inaction for civil society, private sectors and/or public health when no additional risk management or policy making is developed with regard to [name chemical substance]?
2.6	Societal controversy	Do you expect / is there a diversity of opinions on the policy issues with regard to [name of chemical substance]?
2.7	Emerging practices	Are there professional or occupational practices already in place or popping up that take increased environmental health concerns on the exposure to chemical [name chemical substance] into account?
3	Policy relevance	
3.1	Collective action or health promotion is possible	Do you see the need for additional interventions via risk management, environmental or chemical policy measures and/or health prevention promotion with regard to [name chemical substance]?
3.2	Consensus on appropriate responses	Do you expect that agreement on such policy options, measures, interventions will be a relevant factor to find for political decision making with regard to [name chemical substance]?
3.3	Existing policy already (partly) in place Also think of policy evaluation initiatives on the base of time trends	Do you see current policy processes and already agreed policy initiatives at different policy levels (European – local) as a beneficial factor for policy innovation with regard to [name chemical substance]?

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Nr.	Criterion	Question + definitions or relevant sub-criteria
3.4	Need for additional or novel policy? Also think of different policy levels authorised to act, national/regional initiatives additionally needed, need for transversal or cross policy sector cooperation and coordination	How would you appraise the maturity of the current state of policy with regard to [name chemical substance]?
3.5	Multi-level character	Is the differentiation of policy levels (EU, national, regional...) having authority on the matter a potentially hindering factor?
3.6	Need for more horizontal cooperation and policy integration/coordination	To what extent is the transversal nature of the policy theme, policy areas or policy sectors involved relevant?
3.7	Need for more cooperation with NGOs, industry, ...	To what extent is there interdependency of public and private actors to develop and implement policy initiative with regard to [name chemical substance]?
3.8	Costs of inaction expected	Do you expect impactful budgetary costs of inaction for the private and/or public sector with regard to [name chemical substance]?
3.9	Political salience expected Think beyond the competencies of agencies and the administration, for instance discussion in the European or national parliaments, political families and other political decision makers	To what extent do you expect a lot of political interest and sensitivity on the increased health concern on [name chemical substance] for <i>political</i> decision makers

4.3 Results

The questionnaires to appraise the indicator results on Phthalates and DINCH, Cadmium, and PFAS were sent out as soon as T5.4 confirmed the finalised version of the indicator reports. The questionnaires were distributed among the members of the HBM4EU management board, policy board and stakeholder forum. The recipients had a couple of weeks to fill out the questionnaires, namely between 31 January 2022 and 16 February 2022.

The questionnaire on Phthalates and DINCH was filled out by 5 people; the one on PFAS by 6 respondents and the questionnaire on Cadmium by 8. The low response rate per substance group does not allow robust conclusions on the participants' appraisal of the different chemical substances with regard to policy interpretation and translation of aligned study results as visualised in the indicator reports. It also does not allow a comparison or prioritisation of policy opportunities on the base of arguments given on the different scientific, societal and policy relevance. However, the mapping of arguments does lead us to a few insights.

We retrieved core messages out of the input without quoting them literally.

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With regard to PFAS

Especially the PFOS and PFOA-exposure levels are considered too high and a cause for concern, and questions are raised about the other PFASs as well (both long-chain and short-chain perfluorinated chemicals). In the group of respondents, both researchers and societal stakeholders call for action via risk management, environmental and chemical policy measures and health promotion, as they assess the current state of policy-making as rather under-developed. Especially given the recent increase in attention for PFAS hotspots in various countries in Europe, respondents underline the sensitivity of the topic for the public and for political decision makers, given the increased health concern on PFAS. A single respondent also warns for the cost of inaction: not taking sufficient action (both by private and/or public actors) might have impactful budgetary costs. From the results, the respondents highlight the geographical differentiation: most teenagers exceeding the guidance value for PFOS were detected in the studies of Northern Europe and regarding the specific substance PFOA in Western Europe.

With regard to Phthalates and DINCH

Respondents, mainly researchers, signal a need to further regulate not yet restricted phthalates and their substitutes as the exposure of European children to restricted phthalates such as DiBP decreased over the last decade, while exposure to the substitutes has increased. This is an issue of concern because too little is known about their toxicity. While most internal concentrations appear to remain under the guidance values, the presence of many phthalates generally causes concerns, in particular in view of potential additive effects from several phthalates. Respondents indicate that the diversity of opinions on the policy issues that need to be settled with regard to phthalates/DINCH might hamper the effectiveness of policy action. One needs more holistic policy making (surmounting policy sectors). One also needs risk assessment and risk management that tackles the risk of mixture effects, as is underlined by several respondents. On top, more research on the sources of exposure is needed.

With regard to Cadmium

Again, mainly researchers responded and only a few stakeholders. Their core messages on this substance can be summarised as follows: cadmium is still a substance of public health concern and the researchers plea for continued alertness on food and diet, besides tobacco-exposure. There is quite a variation in exposure levels (at least for part of the European population) and in all studies the new alert values for Cadmium are exceeded. Vice versa, researcher-respondents report the absence of decrease in Cd exposure at EU level despite the regulatory interventions implemented. They suggest more dietary recommendations, particularly for vulnerable groups like children and young adults. With regard to scientific uncertainty, the need for the use of health effect indicators is indicated as a knowledge gap in HBM4EU results.

With regard to relevance of the results for policy making respondents indicate that Cadmium is regulated to a large extent already and that it is generally seen as more difficult to implement additional measures. The lack of controversy (no societal or political debate ongoing on the topic) leads weak incentives for policy makers to undertake new policy actions, notwithstanding HBM results indicating the low effectiveness of existing measures.

Given the low response rate on the questionnaires, we added a third stage to our exercise. We asked participants to the 30-31 March 2022 workshop on the aligned study results, to fill out an online (short) survey to help appraise the societal and policy relevance of the Aligned study results as presented during the workshop (see next section).

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5 Stage 3: Appraisal of policy relevance during a workshop by means of a short online survey

5.1 Aim and process

VITO organised a workshop on 30-31 March 2022, in collaboration with EEA and UAntwerpen and dedicated partners for the 4 substance groups: Phthalates/DINCH, PFAS, Cadmium and Bisphenols. The workshop aimed to present and discuss the novel results and messages from the analyses of the Human Biomonitoring data generated via the HBM4EU Aligned Studies.

On the agenda of this workshop were: presentations of indicator results; factual questions and discussion on the messages; break-out groups per substance group and plenary reflection and discussion on the results of the discussion in the two break-out groups per substance. On 30 March 2022, Phthalates/DINCH and PFAS were the central substance groups discussed. On 31 March 2022, the presentations and discussions were centred around Cadmium and Bisphenols. The workshop was attended by (over the two days) 112 participants.

The workshop offered an excellent opportunity to invite participants to fill out a short online survey on the policy and societal relevance of the aligned study results of the 4 substance groups.

In 3.2 section we discuss the content of that questionnaire; in 3.3 the results.

5.2 The online survey for the appraisal of indicator results

For the purpose of the workshop's break-out groups, the long questionnaire was reduced to 6 sharp questions in order to keep the time to fill out the questionnaire limited to 5 minutes. Priority was given to: the appraisal of the gravity of the health risk, the societal resonance expected around the new results from the aligned studies, the respondent's preference for policy options and action as well as the obstacles for further policy development. The question about the groupwise affiliation of the respondents ensured anonymity, so no additional ethics considerations had to be made. In Appendix 4, the short online questionnaire (illustrated for PFAS) can be found.

Most of the response to the online survey came during the workshop days, but as we have sent out a reminder for extra input to the participants by e-mail, we still received some additional responses afterwards. The online survey was closed on April 19, 2022. We received 30 responses on the PFAS questionnaire, 26 on the Phthalates/DINCH questionnaire, 21 on the Bisphenols one and 18 for Cadmium. Both on 30 March and on 31 March, the response rate dropped a bit during the second half of the workshop.

5.3 Results

Given the fact that we 'only' received input of 18 to 30 respondents per substance group, we did not apply sophisticated statistics to analyse the input from this relatively small numbers of participants.

Within a substance group's survey results, we however did compare the responses for the different types of affiliation of the respondents: policy makers and researchers. One should stay very well aware that the low response rates do not allow representative conclusions for any category of affiliation.

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With regard to PFAS

In total 30 people filled out the questionnaire on PFAS. Almost all respondents are affiliated to governments and agencies. Only 1 out of 5 respondents is a researcher.

A large majority (83%) of respondents reports a very strong alert or even alarming results. With a larger proportion of representatives of national or regional governments than from European institutions, more than 3 out of 4 policy representatives also see in the aligned study results on this substance group a strong or even alarming alert. There is concern about the high-end exposures in nearly all countries investigated. The exposure to the "new" PFAS is adding up to that of the "old" PFAS (which do not degrade and will stay in the environment for very long).

A clear majority (70%) expects a strong societal resonance; the same conclusion goes for the group of researchers and the category of policy actors.

When asked what would be your message to your colleagues on the Aligned Study results on PFAS, these were some of the responses: "Many cases above the guidance values"; "concerns about the non-regulated PFAS"; "action must be taken",

When asked for interventions needed, respondents noted: "further regulatory restrictions necessary on use and on presence in environment, drinking water, feed and food; more monitoring and risk assessment needed; regulations (being developed) are very much needed".

More or less one out of 3 participants expect major barriers in the policy making process. This pattern is consistent between both groups of respondents: policy makers and researchers.

With regard to Phthalates/DINCH

26 participants sent in their responses on the Phthalates/DINCH questionnaire. In this group of 26 participants, there approximately 2 out of 3 respondents are affiliated to (national) governments and EU-institutions. Approximately 1 out of 3 respondents is a researcher.

When asked to appreciate the signal value of the Aligned Study results, 80% of the respondents indicated that the results had a "moderate" to "strong" signal value. We saw no difference between policy makers' and researchers' opinions on this moderate/strong signal value of the phthalates/DINCH results.

When asked to formulate messages to communicate to colleagues on the results, respondents indicated that, despite extensive regulations, phthalates can still be found in every single sample investigated. For some highly regulated phthalates levels are above what is considered acceptable. Respondents refer to the use of substitutes and plea for new regulations that regulate phthalates as a group.

60% does not expect more than moderate societal resonance on the aligned study results on phthalates/DINCH, but the category of policy representants slightly more (70%).

What kind of interventions do the respondents suggest? One respondent pleads for continued vigilance, with refined regulation as well as better enforcement of current legislation/regulation. One underlines the importance of regulation on group level and mixture regulation, including operationalisation of the 'essential use' concept. All this, given growing concern about health effects of exposure.

In response to the question: "do you expect that the diversity of opinions in society will hamper further decision-making?", 9 out of 10 participants anticipates that the diversity of opinions will "only slightly" hamper decision-making, while in the category of policy makers this is 8 out of 10.

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With regard to Bisphenols

With 21 responses that came in, a relative smaller number of respondents than for the other substances has filled out the online survey on Bisphenols. From the respondents, only 1 out of 3 is not from government or agency. There was a good balance between policy actors from national or regional governments and from European institutions.

About half of the group reports only a moderate signal value and appraises this substance as nothing to worry for given the exposure being under control. About 1 out of 3 considers the Aligned Study results on Bisphenols to have a „strong“ signal value; when specifically looking at policy-makers' responses, we see that this percentage is about the same (35%).

When asked to formulate messages to communicate to colleagues on the results, respondents indicated that, based on the currently in place TDIs, bisphenols seem of low concern, but there is great uncertainty in the hazard thresholds to allow interpretation of the exposures. Depending on the TDI used for risk assessment, BPA can be a concern.

About 60% does not expect more than moderate societal resonance on the aligned study results on Bisphenols, both in the category of policy representatives and in the category of researchers.

What kind of interventions do the respondents suggest? Respondents indicate that there is a need to consider Bisphenols as a group of concern. Safe alternatives for the use of Bisphenols should be developed. Another suggestion is that we need risk assessment that is widely accepted, on which basis the necessary risk management measures can be taken.

In response to the question: “do you expect that the diversity of opinions in society will hamper further decision-making?”, both 50% of policy makers and researchers anticipate the diversity of opinions will “only slightly” hamper decision-making.

With regard to Cadmium

More than two third of the 18 respondents that responded to the Cadmium questionnaire were affiliated to governments and EU-institutions.

The aligned study results on Cadmium are not perceived as alarming. Most respondents attributed a moderate signal value and more or less one third a strong alert. This pattern is consistent between both groups.

When asked to formulate messages to communicate to colleagues on the results, respondents indicated that, exposure levels remain a concern as levels of cadmium measured seem to be constant the last 10 years. These cadmium levels might be a concern for several population groups. Cadmium, especially from smoking, a vegetarian diet and the application of phosphorus fertilisers in agriculture, contributes to increased body burden.

Half of both the total group of respondents and of the policy representants (55%) expect only moderate societal resonance. Nevertheless about 1 out of 3 policy actors expects the Cadmium results to generate a “strong” societal resonance.

What kind of interventions do the respondents suggest? Many respondents suggest to install incentives that stimulate the use of low Cadmium containing fertilisers. In that context, one mentions the promotion of local food production and recycling, and one suggests putting a stop to the import of fertilizers. Further, more research on the exposure pathways is needed, one states, to further investigate the hypothesis that the main exposure pathway is diet and use of Cd-containing fertilizers.

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More than 50% of the respondents and also of the policy actors in particular expect major barriers in policy making, but nevertheless they do not expect that the obstacles are not surmountable.

Overlooking the appraisal of the Aligned Study results on the four substance groups

When comparing the signal value of the Aligned Study results, we see that the results on PFAS triggers comparatively more societal concern than the other substances groups: with PFAS being attributed mainly “strong” signal value while Phthalates/DINCH and Bisphenols “moderate to strong” and Cadmium “moderate” signal value. This is not unexpected: recent hotspot problems with PFAS contamination in diverse European regions has triggered societal and political concern, and the research results confirm the need for action. This need for policy action is also highly underlined during the workshop and in the online survey that was taken from the participants. Policy-making is starting up, with – in the survey results – a plea for regulation, more monitoring, communication and awareness raising, and risk assessment.

Q5 - For which additional interventions do you see a need with regard to PFAS?

The discussion on Phthalates/DINCH is in another stage of policy-making, as also became clear in the discussion during the workshop and in the survey results. Phthalates have been regulated for a longer time, but from the monitoring results it becomes clear that phthalates can still be found in every single sample investigated. It looks like the policy actions that have been taken, are not effective enough. Respondents of our survey plea for more monitoring to keep the finger on the pulse. On top, respondents are in favour of new and additional regulations that regulate phthalates on a group-basis, given the use of alternatives by the industry that have the same or similar health effects.

Based on the workshop discussions and the survey results, we draw the conclusion that Bisphenols, even after 30 years of attention and the implementation of extensive regulations, still provokes societal controversy. The use of BPF and BPS as alternatives for BPA, make

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respondents plea for regulation on group-basis. On top, respondents underline the need for more investment in solid risk assessment, as there still is uncertainty and controversy on the hazard thresholds that EFSA suggests to interpret the exposures.

From all the substance groups discussed, Cadmium is the substance group of which respondents state that the Aligned Study only have “moderate” signal value. Cadmium is one of the ‘old’ chemicals: it had been regulated already a long time, but from monitoring results it appears that the levels have not dropped significantly over the last 10 years, which incites concern on potential health effects for several population groups. With regard to the interventions needed, respondents request extra regulations, further monitoring and more communication and awareness-raising.

Q5 - For which additional interventions do you see a need with regard to Cadmium?

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6 Appendix 1: SSH-ethics guidelines in case of consultation activities - Summary

Based on the informal note: HBM4EU-policy and guidelines for Ethics Advice in case of research with a Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) component, September 2020

Ilse Loots, UAntwerpen

Ethics requirements for the social sciences and humanities (SSH) are a quality mark and not regulation. The number of consultation initiatives in HBM4EU, for instance in the science-policy nexus, is growing. Therefore, HBM4EU should engage for tailored implementation of the regular SSH-guidelines as a good practice, in line with its general statement on ethics in the Grant Agreement. This of course only applies to consultations that are not included yet in the medical ethics procedures.

The word 'consultation' in the title is used here in its broadest sense: written or oral surveys and questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, expert panels, data retrievals on digital platforms, but also participatory initiatives and dialogues launched in a research context.

The core rule is that you have to apply the SSH ethics procedure as soon as you plan to work with human subjects, whether it be with written or oral surveys and interviews, offline or online experiments, observational research, photographs and other visual material, audio and video recording, focus groups etc. HBM4EU as a forerunner, will opt for a feasible implementation of these rules. The European Commission (2018) does advice research projects to anticipate ethics clearances for SSH research, but only 'if required'. Indeed, reflections on the relevance of ethics considerations prevail over a blind implementation of prescriptions.

We would opt for the following basic requirements:

- a severe policy with regard to the informed consent (in well-argued exceptional circumstances 'oral' instead of 'written');
- the explicit oral or written agreement of participants in bilateral or group sessions in case recording is used (audio/video/pictures/screen shots of non-public digital platforms requiring login and password)
- and a paragraph with ethical considerations and related practical issues in the methods part of any report in which SSH-like research is described or valorised (written or oral surveys and interviews, offline or online experiments, observations, photographs and other visual material, audio and video recording, focus groups etc).

On the other hand, we would opt for a differentiated policy with regard to the additional SSH-ethics approval requirement. The guidelines as summarised in the table below are not meant to discourage consultations, but just anticipate ethics aspects timely and go for a careful research strategy and reporting. In recent years - and at most universities- the Ethics Advice Social Sciences and Humanities (EA SSH) became an essential step in the research cycle. In many areas, scientific journals will increasingly require an ethics committee approval before publication. And for EU-funded SSH-projects, an ethics self-assessment becomes a highly recommended part of the grant agreement (EU-Commission, 2018). We quote: *"Consider that ethics issues arise in many areas of research. Apart from the obvious example, the medical field, research protocols in social sciences, ethnography, psychology, environmental studies, security research, etc. may involve the voluntary participation of research subjects and the collection of data that might be considered as personal. You must protect your volunteers, yourself and your researcher*

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colleagues.” (EU-Commission, 2018, p. 0). A tailored approach also means that a (type of) case by case screening will remain important. Principles and rules of scientific integrity, privacy and ethics might conflict, for instance where we see that downscaling formal and administrative requirements is essential for the participation of more vulnerable groups in HBM-research (Morrens, 2017).

Hence, we do go for a gradual approach as described in the table:

HBM4EU	Position in research cycle				
		before recruitment	during consultation		after
CONSULTATION OF ...	ethics § in research report				
Children (< 18)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> of parent /guardian	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> of parent /guardian	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
(Adult) citizens, consumers, end-users, patients, ...		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other unorganised / nonprofessional stakeholders		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> in case sensitive topic with small non-response risk	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Scientists and researchers, civil servants, authorities and agencies, media and interest groups		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> in case of sensitive topic	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> unless non-response risk	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
National hub members	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		see internal rules	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Stakeholder Forum	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		see internal rules	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	minutes

Notes:

In case of a mixture of target publics: the strictest guideline counts.

‘Unorganised’ is a (target) group or category of people or of organisations having no structure, nor a representative role. Examples are a target group of consumers, a group, vulnerable for a specific exposure in the environment,

The distinct approach for organised and non-organised parties is that HBM4EU has to address science-policy questions to professionally relevant people, familiar with chemicals policy. Their representative role

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does not exclude that they can also speak for themselves, as experienced professionals or volunteers, and not with a strict mandate of their organisation. In case of consultation in platforms that have been installed by HBM4EU, there is an agreement or engagement on each other's roles with regard to the exchange of information and views, so no further SSH-ethics requirements here. In principle, these activities also fit the exclusion criteria from a regular, full ethics advice: the respondents are always adults + data are treated anonymously + no link of the responses to personal or sensitive information + no sensitive topics questioned + no personal or public impact expected for the person in question + interviews are taking place in a (semi-)public space. Of course, all rules with regard to the General Data protection Regulation (GDPR) stay in place. Just mind sensitive topics, for which we do advice to apply for an SSH-ethics approval. Do engage NOT to publish citations of respondents, unless their explicit agreement is provided.

The label 'Position in research cycle' refers to the different stages in the design of a research. The Ethics Advice SSH request and approval needs to precede any stage. There is one exception: a retrospective Ethics Advice SSH can still be granted on request of a researcher who wants to publish the results, but only on condition that all regular ethics requirements were in place during the research (no regularisation for inadmissible activities).

HBM4EU internal regulations are rules, agreed within the Grant agreement, management and consortium, for instance 'Terms of Reference and Rules of Procedure' of the Government Board and the document 'Role, selection criteria and composition' for the Stakeholder forum and the Advisory board.

A next generation HBM4EU could also opt for a column 'Generic approval', applicable to the (future) situation of HBM4EU having its own umbrella ethics authorisation for several similar consultation activities. We do not regard this initiative as prior nor feasible yet in the current HBM4EU project.

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7 Appendix 2: Full version of the questionnaire stage 1

Appraising the policy and social relevance of 'HBM results as visualised by HBM4EU-indicators' for chemical substances: which criteria for prioritisation?

Dear partner in T 5.5 and T 5.4!

In this document we invite you to provide feedback on a list of criteria/factors that could help to prioritise the policy uptake of the indicator results from the aligned studies of HBM4EU. How? This will be explained in the following sections.

If something might not be clear to you after reading this text, please do contact us: happy to provide more information when needed!

1 We welcome your opinion as an environmental health expert!

In this last year of the HBM4EU-project, many new results will become available, in particular the aligned studies' results for the exposure of the European population to different chemical substance groups. Such results will be summarised in the form of 'HBM4EU indicators' for release this autumn. They allow for the monitoring of internal exposure and impact of chemicals as measured in several Human Biomonitoring studies in different EU-regions. The indicators more precisely allow for basic interpretations of the data on:

- the *distribution* of internal exposure in EU populations (median and P95 values);
- the *comparison* of the exposure with *Health-Based Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values* (where available);
- the *geographical comparison* of regions;
- and for some of the substances a comparison over *time* (with a previous European HBM study: DEMOCOPHES).

We got a very nice and appealing preview of the indicators-format during the PFAS-workshop on April 28/29 (by Eva Govarts and Greet Schoeters) as well as during the last HBM4EU Consortium meeting, September 22 (by Jürgen Buekers). You can find a preliminary example for the PFAS substance group in the information package in Appendix. As it is work in progress, we ask you to treat this information **confidentially**. De public release and communication of the indicators for each of the chemical substance groups is expected by the end of 2021.

2 From statistical significance to health concern, societal significance and policy relevance

Which conclusions should be drawn from the indicators? What will be seen as most relevant? Which information could be highlighted by the researchers in order to facilitate its uptake and implementation in policy terms or in managerial and professional practices? Researchers are used to indicate the statistical significance and the comparison of exposure to chemicals with guidance values as a baseline for interpretation. But how will the graphs be received and perceived by professional experts, policy makers and the public at large? A big diversity of factors can be drivers or preconditions of policy response. Once identified, these factors could also be used as criteria to prioritise HBM4EU results or to strengthen the sense of urgency for the uptake of research results by policy makers.

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Before we can ask these type of questions about the ‘HBM indicators’ to relevant groups of stakeholders (scientists, policy- and decision makers, stakeholders), we want to develop a list of criteria that can help to prioritise indicator results. In concrete terms, we would like to hear from you whether the list of criteria in section 3 of this document is sufficiently solid and/or still needs adjustment before asking different types of stakeholders to fill it out (for different substance groups). Below you can find a scheme visualising the stepwise approach we have in mind. Additional explanation about the why of such an exercise can be found at the very end of this document.

3 Criteria list to check

What do you think are good reasons to bring HBM4EU results to the attention of policymakers and society as a matter of priority? What might strengthen the arguments for policy uptake and implementation? These are the questions that you should bear in mind when going through the table below.

Practically, how to proceed? Consider each criterion in the list (row per row), and fill out the columns as requested. It looks like a long list, but you will move quickly through it. Use a generic perspective, so: regardless of a specific group of chemicals. In the last column you have the opportunity to comment on the criterium and (if you like) you can reflect on it (exemplary) from the perspective of a specific substance.

We deliberately chose to send you a Word document in which you can add remarks in the margin of the text or add text to e.g. the definition of a criterium. Please do make use of the opportunity to add your comments or add text, making use of the ‘track changes’ option in Word.

Nr.	Criterion Note: in the end these criteria will serve as questions to ask for feedback from experts in a specific substance group, see also °°	Relevant aspects/sub-criteria may include:	Yes, relevant criterion (please indicate how relevant) *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial	No, not a relevant criterion in my opinion	Do you have a comment / example, e.g. from the PFAS-context, on this criterion ?
1	Scientific relevance				
1.1	Health concern (hazard)	Type of effects, exceedance of HBGV's, time trends, vulnerability of specific groups, ...	* ** ***		
1.2	Extent of the risk	Population(s) at risk, susceptibility, number(s) of exposed people, persistency, impact on future generations, ...	* ** ***		
1.3	Scientific evidence and robustness	Robust knowledge on exposure-effect associations, knowledge on sources and exposure pathways, acquired consensus under scientific peers ...	* ** ***		
1.4	Complexity and scientific uncertainty*	Knowledge- and data gaps, scientific uncertainty, disagreement between expert groups	* ** ***		
	Did you miss any criterion in group 1 above ?		Yes	No	If yes, I missed ...

Nr.	Criterion Note: in the end these criteria will serve as questions to ask for feedback from experts in a specific substance group, see also °°	Relevant aspects/sub-criteria may include:	Yes, relevant criterion (please indicate how relevant) *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial	No, not a relevant criterion in my opinion	Do you have a comment / example, e.g. from the PFAS-context, on this criterion ?
	Should we differentiate some of the listed criteria for application at the EU-level versus the member state level ?		Yes	No	If yes, for which criteria numbers should we differentiate? ...
	Indicate the criteria that were not clear to you (in track changes or in a comment)				
	Other comments to make?		Yes	No	If yes, please formulate your comment here.
2	Societal relevance				
2.1	Risk perception	Public concern, willingness to act	* ** ***		
2.2	Societal resonance	Agenda-setting at political level, by civil society organisations and networks and/or in the	* ** ***		

Nr.	Criterion Note: in the end these criteria will serve as questions to ask for feedback from experts in a specific substance group, see also °°	Relevant aspects/sub-criteria may include:	Yes, relevant criterion (please indicate how relevant) *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial	No, not a relevant criterion in my opinion	Do you have a comment / example, e.g. from the PFAS-context, on this criterion ?
		media, social amplification of risk			
2.3	Social inequality in exposure, effects, risk	Higher health risk or concerns for socially vulnerable groups?	* ** ***		
2.4	Socio-economic consequences	Socio-economic and vested interests;	* ** ***		
2.5	Costs of inaction expected	Impactful (monetary health) costs of inaction expected for sectors	* ** ***		
2.6	Normative character	Diversity of opinions on the issue based on differences in norms and values	* ** ***		
2.7	Emerging practices	Professional practices (popping up or vested) already taking this knowledge into account	* ** ***		

Nr.	Criterion <u>Note:</u> in the end these criteria will serve as questions to ask for feedback from experts in a specific substance group, see also °°	Relevant aspects/sub-criteria may include:	Yes, relevant criterion (please indicate how relevant) *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial	No, not a relevant criterion in my opinion	Do you have a comment / example, e.g. from the PFAS-context, on this criterion ?
	Did you miss any criterion in group 2 above ?		Yes	No	If yes: I missed ...
	Should we differentiate some of the listed criteria for application at the EU-level versus the member state level ?		Yes	No	If yes, for which criteria numbers should we differentiate? ...
	Indicate the criteria that were not clear to you (in track changes or in a comment)				
	Other comments to make?		Yes	No	If yes, please formulate your comment here.

Nr.	Criterion Note: in the end these criteria will serve as questions to ask for feedback from experts in a specific substance group, see also °°	Relevant aspects/sub-criteria may include:	Yes, relevant criterion (please indicate how relevant) *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial	No, not a relevant criterion in my opinion	Do you have a comment / example, e.g. from the PFAS-context, on this criterion ?
3	Policy relevance				
3.1	Collective (preventive) action or health promotion is possible	Opportunities for intervention via environmental or chemical policy or health prevention promotion	* ** ***		
3.2	Consensus on appropriate responses	Agreement on policy options, measures, interventions	* ** ***		
3.3	Existing policy already (partly) in place	Current policy processes and agreed policy initiatives at different policy levels (European – local)	* ** ***		
3.4	Need for (additional or novel) policy	Maturity of current policy: underdeveloped, in full development, well-developed	* ** ***		
3.5	Multi-level character	Policy levels authorised to act, the policy level differentiation. Not only relevant for EU-actors but also national/regional initiatives needed	* ** ***		

Nr.	Criterion <u>Note:</u> in the end these criteria will serve as questions to ask for feedback from experts in a specific substance group, see also °°	Relevant aspects/sub-criteria may include:	Yes, relevant criterion (please indicate how relevant) *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial	No, not a relevant criterion in my opinion	Do you have a comment / example, e.g. from the PFAS-context, on this criterion ?
3.6	Need for more cooperation and policy integration	Transversal nature of the policy theme, policy areas or policy sectors involved	* ** ***		
3.7	Need for more multi-actor cooperation	Interdependency of public and private actors to develop and implement policy initiative	* ** ***		
3.8	Costs of inaction expected	Impactful budgetary costs of inaction expected for the public sector	* ** ***		
3.9	Political salience	Interest and sensitivity of the issue for <i>political</i> decision makers beyond agencies and the administration (for instance in parliament, for political families)	* ** ***		
	Did you miss any criterion in group 3 above ?		Yes	No	If yes: I missed ...

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Nr.	Criterion Note: in the end these criteria will serve as questions to ask for feedback from experts in a specific substance group, see also °°	Relevant aspects/sub-criteria may include:	Yes, relevant criterion (please indicate how relevant) *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial	No, not a relevant criterion in my opinion	Do you have a comment / example, e.g. from the PFAS-context, on this criterion ?
	Should we differentiate some of the listed criteria for application at the EU-level versus the member state level ?		Yes	No	If yes, for which criteria numbers should we differentiate? ...
	Indicate the criteria that were not clear to you (in track changes or in a comment)				
	Other comments to make?		Yes	No	If yes, please formulate your comment here.

°Partly based on similar consultations (Keune et al, 2009; Coertjens et al, 2018) and literature (Klinke & Renn, 2002; Renn, 2005; Renn 2017; De Hollander & Hanemaaijer, 2003, Sumner et al., Health Research Policy and Systems 2011, 9 (Suppl 1):S3 <http://www.biomedcentral.com/1478-4505/9/S1/S3>).

°°With regard to how we define criteria: we tried to formulate them in a way that they can only be understood in one way. However, we acknowledge that in some cases a criterium can be interpreted positively (adding to the argument that policy uptake is needed) or negatively (giving arguments contra). Consider for instance the criterion of remaining scientific uncertainty or disagreement: this can be a disadvantage for policy uptake but also a good reason to apply the precautionary principle.

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4 This consultation is data-protected

We only use your input on an aggregated level and will never link your answers to your name or affiliation. Moreover, if a quote is interesting to illustratively include in a report – always anonymously – we will only do so after asking for your explicit consent.

We greatly appreciate your opinion and input and are happy to accept it **by November 8**.

5 Additional explanation: why an upcoming consultation on HBM4EU-indicators?

This consultation, asking you to provide feedback on the list of criteria to appraise the societal, scientific and policy relevance of the HBM4EU indicators on the aligned studies, is a first step in a consultation process in which we will ask different types of stakeholders to appraise the information from the HBM4EU indicators. The reasons why we intend to have this consultation are at least twofold. (1) Because we expect that the HBM4EU indicators will be interpreted and used in different ways after their release and we value the stakeholders' appraisal as an interesting source of additional information. (2) Results of the HBM4EU aligned studies will anyway be contextualised in the diversity of European and national policy, in relation to other types of knowledge, previous policy initiatives, knowledge about solutions and societal concerns. Moreover, different opinions and considerations may exist, especially where policy options are still under negotiation or where uncertainty issues play a role. We would like to prospect and create transparency on this scientific, policy and societal significance and to stimulate the extraction of conclusions or main messages.

Therefore, HBM4EU's T.5.5 wants to organise a consultation after the release of the HBM4EU indicators, probing for the meaning that different groups attach to the exposure and impact indicators. In this stage 2, scientific experts will be in first instance invited to appraise the results for the scientific criteria, policy actors for the policy-relevant criteria and societal stakeholders for the societal criteria.

Complementary to this usual division of tasks, we acknowledge that environmental health researchers operate as boundary workers towards policy needs. These experts are often well informed on societal concerns and political agenda opportunities, based on their day-to-day experience working on the interface of science and policy. Further we acknowledge that policy makers used to working with HBM and public advocacy groups may also have a good overview of relevant environmental health knowledge; they also know how to formulate and raise policy relevant research-oriented questions. This explains why we plan to create openness for 'cross-border' filling out the criteria-list in a next stage. Respondents will get the opportunity to provide input on all 3 categories: scientific relevance, societal relevance and policy relevance.

In the table below, we visualise how the questionnaire in a next stage would look like. Based on your input on the aforementioned table we might finetune the content. We might also choose for an online survey format to receive stakeholders' input in a more convenient way.

Nr.	Criterion	Your score for this criterion?	What message would you advise your organisation to tweet, regarding this criterion, based on your reading of the HBM indicators?				
		For PFASs	For Cadmium	For Bisphenols	For PAHs	For Phthalates & DINCH	
		None * ** ***	None * ** ***	None * ** ***	None * ** ***		
1	Scientific relevance						
1.1							
1.2							
1.3							
1.4							
2	Societal relevance						
2.1							
2.2							
2.3							
2.4							
2.5							
2.6							
2.7							
3	Policy relevance						
3.0							
3.1							
3.2							
3.3							
3.4							
3.5							
3.6							
3.7							
3.8							
3.9							

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The ultimate goal of the consultation is not to rank or prioritise substance groups, nor to use a fixed multi-criteria assessment methodology, but to map the divergence of opinions on the different chemicals, based on people's reading of the HBM indicators. Such an appraisal is therefore clearly different from and complementary to the 3 fruitful prioritisation processes of substances of HBM4EU in which responsible governments and national hubs participated.

By launching this consultation, we hope to: increase insight into the level of agreement on the solidity of the knowledge base, identify specific policy opportunities and give clarity on the societal desire to take policy action. This exercise can also increase awareness on the results among a broader diversity of actors. In this way, this mapping of arguments can inform policy makers when taking further policy steps.

We greatly appreciate your opinion and input and await your response by November 8.

Yours sincerely,

Ann Crabbé, Dries Coertjens & Ilse Loots, T 5.5 researchers

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8 Appendix 3: Full version of the questionnaire stage 2 (exemplary for one substance group)

Questionnaire on Phthalates and substitute Hexamoll DINCH	
<p>A. What message would you recommend your organisation to tweet publicly on the aligned study results on Phthalates, on the base of the (draft) HBM4EU indicator presented?</p> <p><i>Mind that the indicator is at this moment still to be treated confidentially.</i></p>	<p>My tweet:</p>
<p>B. What core message would you recommend to inform your colleagues in the organisation on the aligned study results on Phthalates, on the base of the (draft) HBM4EU indicator presented?</p> <p><i>Mind that the indicator is at this moment still to be treated confidentially.</i></p>	<p>My core message:</p>
<p>The next rows of the table contain questions on 1. the health significance of these aligned study results on Phthalates, on 2. the estimated societal relevance and 3. on the soundness of these results for risk management and policy making.</p> <p>I am ... (if multiple roles apply, please indicate with 1st, 2nd, 3rd which group you belong most to):</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> An environmental/health expert or risk assessor, please fill out <u>at least</u> the questions in Group 1. Scientific relevance</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Societal stakeholder, please fill out <u>at least</u> the questions in Group 2. Societal relevance</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Regulatory and/or policy expert or risk manager, please fill out <u>at least</u> the questions in Group 3. Policy relevance</p> <p>Please appraise the criteria one by one, giving priority to the criteria for the group you belong most to; we however also welcome your opinion very much in the other sections!</p> <p>Comment field for additional remarks</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; height: 80px; width: 100%;"></div>	

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Nr.	Criterion	Question + definitions or relevant sub-criteria	Your answer	Do you have a comment, an example or a good reference to information for documenting this particular criterion in this context?
1	Scientific relevance			
1.1	Exposure concern Think of: number(s) of people exposed, geographical distribution, time trends, higher exposed subgroups of population, knowledge on sources, lifestyle and exposure pathways ...	To what extent do the values of the HBM4EU indicator on Phthalates legitimise an increased <u>exposure concern</u>?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial <i>Just mark your answer.</i>	
1.2	Health concern (hazard) Also think of type of effects, mixture effects, persistence of substance, type of vulnerable groups, ...	To what extent do the values of the HBM4EU indicator on Phthalates legitimise an increased <u>health concern</u>?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial	
1.3	Extent of the risk Risk = hazard * exposure. Think of numbers or % exposed exceeding HBM-GV, but if no exceedance also the relevance for health impacts, groups or behaviour patterns correlated with higher risk, population(s) at risk, burden of disease, impact on future generations, ...	To what extent do the values of the HBM4EU indicator on Phthalates legitimise an increased <u>risk concern</u>?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial	

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Nr.	Criterion	Question + definitions or relevant sub-criteria	Your answer	Do you have a comment, an example or a good reference to information for documenting this particular criterion in this context?
1.4	Scientific evidence and robustness of knowledge base with regard to hazard (exposure-effect associations) Evidence refers to sufficient, robust expert knowledge and also to acquired consensus under scientific peers, ...	Do the values of the HBM4EU indicator on Phthalates in your opinion strengthen the evidence base or knowledge robustness with regard to hazard (exposure-effect associations) for risk management or policy measures?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial	
1.5	Scientific evidence and robustness of knowledge base with regard to exposure pathways and sources Evidence refers to sufficient, robust expert knowledge and also to acquired consensus under scientific peers, ...	Do the values of the HBM4EU indicator on Phthalates in your opinion strengthen the evidence base or knowledge robustness with regard to exposure pathways and sources for risk management or policy measures?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial	
1.6	Knowledge gaps and scientific uncertainty Notwithstanding the available scientific evidence, there can still be relevant knowledge- and data gaps, scientific uncertainty, or remaining disagreement between expert groups on one or more of the items 1.1-1.3, as observable in scientific literature, studies, on conferences, ...	Do you still see knowledge gaps or scientific uncertainty in the knowledge base on Phthalates that might hamper additional risk management or policy measures? (despite the information presented in the HBM4EU indicator)?	- no *do not know **maybe ***yes, sure	
Did you miss any criterion in group 1 above?			No	Yes If yes, I missed ...

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Nr.	Criterion	Question + definitions or relevant sub-criteria	Your answer	Do you have a comment, an example or a good reference to information for documenting this particular criterion in this context?	
		Would you prefer to differentiate your answer on one or more of the listed criteria for application at the EU-level versus the member state level? For instance, for differentiating the appraisal of 'risk' geographically, for a 'hot spot' approach, the potential and scope for additional measures under national/regional/local governance, ...	No	Yes	If yes, for which criteria number(s) is differentiation relevant in your opinion? Why?
Indicate the criteria numbers that were not clear to you (in track changes or in a comment)					
Do you have other comments on the list and your answers above?			No	Yes	If yes, please leave your comment here.
2	Societal relevance				
2.1	Risk perception As a driver for risk management and policy making, willingness to act, possibility to act (labelling, SIN-list, ...)?	How relevant in your opinion with regard to Phthalates is public concern of consumers or citizens	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial		
2.2	Societal resonance Think of civil society organisations/networks pressing on the public/political agenda, NGO activity, attention for Phthalates in the media, social amplification of risk	How relevant in your opinion is lobbying by civil society organisations as a driver for risk management and policy making on Phthalates?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial		
2.3	Social inequality in exposure, effects, risk	Do you consider higher health risk or concerns for <i>socially</i> vulnerable groups (lower SES) a good driver for risk management measures or policy making with regard to Phthalates?	- no *do not know **maybe ***yes, sure		

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Nr.	Criterion	Question + definitions or relevant sub-criteria	Your answer	Do you have a comment, an example or a good reference to information for documenting this particular criterion in this context?	
2.4	Socio-economic consequences	How much relevance or impact in your opinion have socio-economic and vested interests on dealing with additional risk regulation, management and policy with regard to Phthalates?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial		
2.5	Costs of inaction expected	Do you expect impactful (monetary health) costs of inaction for civil society, private sectors and/or public health when no additional risk management or policy making is developed with regard to Phthalates?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial		
2.6	Societal controversy	Do you expect / is there a diversity of opinions on the policy issues with regard to Phthalates?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial		
2.7	Emerging practices	Are there professional or occupational practices already in place or popping up that take increased environmental health concerns on the exposure to Phthalates into account?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial		
Did you miss any criterion in group 2 above?			Yes	No	If yes: I missed ...

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Nr.	Criterion	Question + definitions or relevant sub-criteria	Your answer	Do you have a comment, an example or a good reference to information for documenting this particular criterion in this context?	
		Would you prefer to differentiate your answer on one or more of the listed criteria for application at the EU-level versus the member state level? For instance, for differentiating the appraisal of 'risk' geographically, for a 'hot spots' approach, the potential and scope for additional measures under national/regional/local governance, ...	Yes	No	If yes, for which criteria number(s) is differentiation relevant in your opinion? Why?
Indicate the criteria that were not clear to you (in track changes or in a comment)					
Other comments to make?			Yes	No	If yes, please formulate your comment here.
3	Policy relevance				
3.1	Collective action or health promotion is possible	Do you see the need for additional interventions via risk management, environmental or chemical policy measures and/or health prevention promotion with regard to Phthalates?	- no *yes, but just relevant **yes, very much ***yes, strongly		If yes, please specify here.
3.2	Consensus on appropriate responses	Do you expect that agreement on such policy options, measures, interventions will be a relevant factor to find for political decision making with regard to Phthalates?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial		What might hamper taking appropriate responses?
3.3	Existing policy already (partly) in place Also think of policy evaluation initiatives on the base of time trends	Do you see current policy processes and already agreed policy initiatives at different policy levels (European – local) as a beneficial factor for policy innovation with regard to Phthalates?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial		

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Nr.	Criterion	Question + definitions or relevant sub-criteria	Your answer	Do you have a comment, an example or a good reference to information for documenting this particular criterion in this context?	
3.4	Need for additional or novel policy? Also think of different policy levels authorised to act, national/regional initiatives additionally needed, need for transversal or cross policy sector cooperation and coordination	How would you appraise the maturity of the current state of policy with regard to Phthalates?	- factor of no relevance to me *underdeveloped **in full development ***well-developed		We very much welcome specifications and comments here.
3.5	Multi-level character	Is the differentiation of policy levels (EU, national, regional...) having authority on the matter a potentially hindering factor?	- factor of no relevance to me * just relevant ** very relevant ***crucial		
3.6	Need for more horizontal cooperation and policy integration/coordination	To what extent is the transversal nature of the policy theme, policy areas or policy sectors involved relevant?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial		
3.7	Need for more cooperation with NGOs, industry, ...	To what extent is there interdependency of public and private actors to develop and implement policy initiative with regard to Phthalates?	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial		
3.8	Costs of inaction expected	Do you expect impactful budgetary costs of inaction for the private and/or public sector with regard to Phthalates?	- no relevance *just impactful **very impactful ***crucial		

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Nr.	Criterion	Question + definitions or relevant sub-criteria	Your answer	Do you have a comment, an example or a good reference to information for documenting this particular criterion in this context?	
3.9	Political salience expected Think beyond the competencies of agencies and the administration, for instance discussion in the European or national parliaments, political families and other political decision makers	To what extent do you expect a lot of political interest and sensitivity on the increased health concern on Phthalates for <i>political</i> decision makers	- no relevance *just relevant **very relevant ***crucial		
Did you miss any criterion in group 3 above?			Yes	No	If yes: I missed ...
Would you prefer to differentiate your answer on one or more of the listed criteria for application at the EU-level versus the member state level? For instance, for differentiating the appraisal of 'risk' geographically, for a 'hot spots' approach, the potential and scope for additional measures under national/regional/local governance, ...			Yes	No	If yes, for which criteria number(s) is differentiation relevant in your opinion? Why?
Indicate the criteria that were not clear to you (in track changes or in a comment)					
Other comments to make?			Yes	No	If yes, please formulate your comment here.

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9 Appendix 4: Full version of the online workshop questionnaire (exemplary for one substance group)

This more compressed questionnaire was formatted in Qualtrics. It could be opened via a weblink and a QR-code on a mobile phone in order not to disturb the participant's screen for attendance of the workshop's sessions at the same time.

Survey on PFAS

This is an anonymous questionnaire, but we would like to know **to which group you belong (the most)**:

EU institution or EU agency
 National or regional government
 University or research institute
 Societal stakeholder (NGO, industry, ...)

Do the aligned study results on PFAS in your opinion **reveal or legitimize an increased (exposure or health) concern?**

No signal value
 Moderate signal value
 Strong alert
 Alarming values

Reflecting back on the presentations of today: **what core message would you communicate to inform your colleagues** - in your own organisation - on the aligned study results on PFAS? (Although today still confidential)

To what extent do you expect these aligned study results on PFAS to trigger or receive **societal resonance** (from stakeholders, politicians, the public, press, ...)?

No societal resonance
 Moderate resonance
 Strong resonance
 Alerts

For which **additional interventions** do you see a need with regard to PFAS?

Monitoring
 Risk assessment
 Environmental or chemical regulation
 Enforcement of current regulation
 Economic incentives (taxes, subsidies)
 Promoting the use of alternatives

Communication and awareness raising
 Disease prevention/health promotion by the **public sector**
 Disease prevention/health promotion by the **private sector**
 Other:

Which (policy) initiative do you personally think is **most urgently needed?**

Do you expect a diversity of opinions in society, in the Union or in member states to hamper the further development of risk management and decision making on PFAS?

No
 Yes, but slightly
 Yes, major barrier(s)
 Insurmountable barrier(s)

Powered by Qualtrics